

1 UAS MODELING PROFILE - UAS STRUCTURAL STEREOTYPES

A UAS consists of a UAV(s), a mission assigned to it, its location, state, goals, altitude, speed, and heading during the mission, the environment in which it operates, its neighboring UAV(s), and its connections with the GPS, RC, and the GCS. The aim of UAS structural stereotypes is to allow the *Software Engineer* to specify the structural details of the self-adaptation during UML class diagram modeling. Figure 1 shows UAS structural stereotypes.

As shown in the figure, the stereotypes defining UAS concepts are an extension of the UML metaclass *Class*. A total of ten stereotypes are defined in the *UAS Structural* package of the UAS UML profile. The mandatory stereotypes in *red* color are the core of the UAS mission, necessary for the *Software Engineer* to specify during the UAS application software class diagram modeling. Following, we explain each of the UAS structural stereotypes.

- *MissionStatus*: It is a mandatory stereotype, defined to model a class that contains information about the current status of the UAS mission. A UAS mission status includes the current waypoint, number of waypoints covered, distance covered by the UAV, etc. It is a mandatory stereotype, applied to a class (that specifies UAS mission status) in the UAS mission class diagram.
- *UAV*: A UAV is the main entity in the UAS. Each mission requires a UAV(s) for its execution. It is a mandatory stereotype, applied to a UAV class that captures variables related to a particular UAV such as its ID or its role in the mission. Examples of UAVs are *fixed-wing* UAVs or *quad-copter* UAVs.
- *GoalStatus*: Each mission has a goal(s) that the UAS has to satisfy. It is an optional stereotype, applied to a class that specifies the current status of UAS goals. Examples of UAS mission goals are *track traffic signal violating vehicle*, *avoid collision*, or *ensure safety*.
- *LocationStatus*: This stereotype is applied to a class that captures the location of a UAV. It is a mandatory stereotype. Location can be defined as latitude and longitude.
- *ConnectionStatus*: During a mission, a UAV is connected to its GCS (Ground Control Station), a GPS, and an RC. The *ConnectionStatus* stereotype is applied to a class that captures the status of a UAV's connection to its GCS, GPS, and RC. A UAV's connection status determines the need for a UAS to adapt its behavior. It is a mandatory stereotype.
- *SpeedStatus*: This stereotype is applied to a class that captures the current and expected speed of a UAV during its mission. It is a mandatory stereotype.
- *AltitudeStatus*: This stereotype is applied to a class that captures a UAV's current and expected altitude during its mission. It is a mandatory stereotype.
- *EnvironmentStatus*: It is an optional stereotype, applied to a class that defines any known environmental factor that has an impact on the UAS during the mission execution. Modeling this allows the users to check if the UAS is correctly adapting its behavior in case of a weather change or obstacles in the environment. Examples of this stereotype are trees, buildings, wind, rain, or haze.
- *HeadingStatus*: This stereotype is applied to a class that captures the current and expected heading of a UAV during its mission. It is a mandatory stereotype.
- *StateStatus*: This stereotype captures the current and expected state (as per the UML state machine) during the mission. For example, *GotoWaypoint*, *RTL*, or *Waiting*. It is a mandatory stereotype.
- *MissionStatus*: This stereotype is applied to a class that captures the status of the UAS mission in execution. For example, the flight time, waypoints covered, current waypoint, etc. It is a mandatory stereotype.

2 UAS MODELING PROFILE – CHANGE STEREOTYPES

During a UAS mission, there are certain types of changes that can occur. These are the changes that require the UAVs in a UAS to adapt to another behavior. To allow the *Software Engineer* to model these changes, we define UAS change-related stereotypes. These stereotypes refer to the changes in the UAS, in the environment, and the operational needs of a UAS mission [1]. Figure 2 shows the UAS UML profile change stereotypes. These stereotypes allow the *Software Engineer* to model the types of changes during UAS mission behavioral modeling. The stereotypes are an extension of the UML metaclass *Transition*. There is a total of eight stereotypes in the UAS UML profile change package. There are three types of changes that can occur in a UAS mission, i.e., changes in the UAS, changes in the environment, and changes in the operational needs.

- *ChangeInUAS*: It is an abstract stereotype. It is used to model various types of change in the UAS. These changes include changes in the UAV itself, its neighbor, and the GCS controlling the UAV.
- *UAVChange*: It is an extension of the *ChangeInUAS* stereotype. It is applied to a transition in a UML state machine that is fired in case of a change in the UAV. Examples of changes in UAVs are battery discharge, GPS loss, or terrain data loss.

- *NeighborChange*: It is also an extension of the *ChangeInUAS* stereotype. It is applied to a transition that is fired in case of change in the neighbor of a UAV. Examples of changes in neighbor include failure of the neighbor to perform the assigned task (due to a crash or any other reason).
- *GCSChange*: It is also an extension of the *ChangeInUAS* stereotype. It is applied on a transition that is fired in case of change in the Ground Control Station (GCS). GCS is responsible for giving commands and controlling the UAS. An example of change in GCS is a disconnection between a UAV and the GCS.
- *ChangeInEnvironment*: It is an abstract stereotype. It models the changes that occur in the operating environment during the UAS mission. These changes can be an identification of obstacles during flight or changes in the weather.
- *WeatherChange*: It is applied on a transition that is fired in case of a change in the weather. Weather changes have an impact on the UAS and require self-adaptive behavior. The weather changes include increased wind speed, haze, or rain.
- *ObstacleNearby*: It is applied on a transition that is fired in case of identification of a nearby obstacle. The obstacles include other UAVs, buildings, or trees.
- *OperationalChange*: It refers to the changes that occur in the operational needs of a UAS during mission execution and may require a change in mission *Goals*. It is applied on a transition that is fired in case of a change in the operational needs of a UAV. Considering an example of the traffic monitoring mission. A battery discharge requires a UAV to adapt its goal from *Tracking* to *RTL*.

3 UAS MODELING PROFILE - ADAPTATION STEREOTYPES

In this section, we describe the stereotypes that are defined to specify the adaptation alternatives for UAS during mission execution. These stereotypes allow the *Software Engineer* to model the solutions (adaptation alternatives) to handle the changes that occur. Once a change is identified, the UAV alters its actions, its payload's action, or its goal. Figure 3 shows the UAS UML profile adaptation stereotypes. The adaptation stereotypes have three main stereotypes: (i) *UAV-Action-Adaptation*, (ii) *Payload-Action-Adaptation*, and (iii) *Goal*. The *UAV-Action-Adaptation* and *Payload-Action-Adaptation* are an extension of the UML metaclass *OpaqueBehavior* and are modeled as actions (effect) on the transition of the UML state machine. The *UAV-Action-Adaptation* stereotype refers to an action that requires adaptation in a UAV. For example, to wait, to land, or to adapt its speed. It has a *value* attribute of data type *String*, which allows specifying the value of an action. For example, if the speed of the UAV is to be increased and the new speed value is 7m/s then the value attribute contains this value. For the possible UAV actions, we have analyzed three open-source mission planning tools, i.e., UgCS [2], Mission Planner [3], and QGroundControl [4]. This analysis helped to extract the stereotypes for *UAV-Action-Adaptation*, i.e., *Takeoff*, *Land*, *RTL*, *SetFlightHeight*, *DecreaseHorizontalSpeed*, *IncreaseHorizontalSpeed*, *DecreaseVerticleSpeed*, *IncreaseVerticleSpeed*, *SetRelay*, *SetServo*, *SetDirection*, *Wait*, *Loiter*, *Jump*, *SetROI*, *AdaptPosition*, *AdaptWaypoint*, and *SendMessage*.

- The *Land*, and *RTL* stereotypes are applied to the land, and return-to-launch actions of a UAV. These actions occur as a result of a change transition.
- The *SetTurnType* allows specifying how the UAV passes through a waypoint. For example, *spline* or *stop and turn*.
- The *SetFlightHeight* stereotype allows the definition of the adaptation in altitude that the UAV should attain during its mission or at a particular waypoint.
- The *Speed* stereotype defines the adaptation in the speed of the UAV for the complete mission or after a particular waypoint. This stereotype has four extensions, *DecreaseHorizontalSpeed*, *IncreaseHorizontalSpeed*, *DecreaseVerticleSpeed*, and *IncreaseVerticleSpeed*. The stereotypes for horizontal speed allow defining the increase and decrease adaptation in the horizontal speed of the UAV during the mission. The stereotypes for vertical speed allow for defining the increase and decrease adaptation in the vertical speed of the UAV during the mission.
- The *SetRelay* stereotype allows adapting the UAV action by using it to send a signal, for example, to broadcast a person's mobile signal. It has three attributes *relayID*, *relayRepeat*, and *relayDelay*. The *relayID* attribute allows specifying the relay number to be switched on. The *relayRepeat* attribute specifies if the relay action is to be set to repeat. The *relayDelay* allows specifying the delay between relay signals. The inherited value attribute allows specifying if a relay is on or off.
- The *SetServo* stereotype allows defining the adaptation in servo, i.e., if a particular servo is required to be set as a result of a change. This stereotype has four attributes *servoID*, *servoPWM*, *servoCycleCount*, and *servoDelay*. The *servoID* attribute allows specifying the servo number that is to be switched on. The *servoPWM* attribute is the signal sent to the servo. *PWM* specifies times per second, the signal is sent. The *servoCycleCount* attribute allows specifying the number of times a signal is to be sent to a particular servo. The *ServoDelay* attribute allows specifying the delay between servo signals. The inherited value attribute allows specifying the on or off value of the selected servo.
- The *SetDirection* stereotype allows specifying adaptation in the direction of the UAV during its flight. This stereotype is defined by specifying the value of any of its four attributes, i.e., *yawAngle*, *yawAngleRelativeTo*, *roll*, and *pitch*. The *yawAngle* specifies the angle of the UAV nose pointing from left to right, its value is between 0° and 360° . The *yawAngleRelativeTo* attribute specifies the angle of yaw that it is relative to,

Fig. 1. UAS Structural Stereotypes

Fig. 2. Change Stereotypes

Fig. 3. Adaptation Stereotypes

Fig. 4. UAS Modeling Profile

it is relative to the next waypoint, or is relative to the north [2]. The *pitch* attribute specifies the up and down movement of the UAV's nose, it is specified in degrees. The *roll* attribute specifies UAV's rotation about its axis, it is specified in degrees.

- The *Wait* stereotype allows defining the waiting action of the UAV as a result of a change. It has three attributes, *waitUnlimited*, *waitDuration*, and *waitAltitude*. The *waitUnlimited* attribute allows specifying if the UAV should wait at a point for an unlimited time or until the next command is received. The *waitDuration* attribute allows specifying the duration in seconds for which the UAV should wait. The *waitAltitude* attribute specifies the Altitude that the UAV should maintain while waiting.
- The *Loiter* stereotype allows defining the loiter action, i.e., the UAV flying over a small area repeatedly, as a result of a change. For example, UAVs loitering over seashore to identify drowning swimmers. It has four attributes as, *loiterUnlimited*, *loiterDuration*, *loiterCycle*, *loiterAltitude*. The *loiterUnlimited* attribute allows specifying if the UAV has to loiter over an area for an unlimited time or until the UAV receives the next command. The *loiterDuration* attribute specifies the duration in seconds or hours for which the UAV should loiter over an area. The *loiterCycle* specifies the number of cycles the UAV should fly for over the specified waypoints. The *loiterAltitude* specifies the altitude that the UAV has to maintain while loitering.
- The *Jump* stereotype allows defining an adaptation in the *Jump* action of the UAV from a particular waypoint. For example, whenever the UAV reaches waypoint 4, it should jump back to waypoint 2. This stereotype consists of two attributes *jumpToWaypoint* and *jumpUnlimited*. The *jumpToWaypoint* specifies the waypoint at which the UAV should jump when it reaches a particular waypoint let's say 'x'. The *jumpUnlimited* specifies if the UAV should jump to the specified waypoint whenever it reaches the waypoint 'x', for an unlimited time.

The *Payload-Action-Adaptation* stereotype is applied to an action of a transition that requires an adaptation in a payload's action. For example, taking a photo or turning on the fire extinguisher. This stereotype has two attributes, *name* and *action*. The *name* attribute allows specifying the name of the payload, for example, fire extinguisher. The *action* attribute specifies the action required by the payload, for example, to turn on the fire extinguisher.

The *CameraAction* stereotype is an extension of the *Payload-Action-Adaptation* stereotype. This stereotype allows specifying different camera actions in detail. This stereotype has attributes *mode*, *recording*, *panorama*, *numberOfShots*, *firstShotDelay*, *timeIntervalBetweenShots*, *distanceBetweenShots*, *directionAngle*, *angleOfRotation*. The *mode* attribute allows specifying the mode of the camera, i.e., video or photo. The *recording* attribute allows specifying when the video recording is to be turned on and when it is to be turned off. The *panorama* attribute allows specifying if a panorama action is required by the payload. Its value is *true* or *false*. Also, if the camera mode is set to video the camera makes a panorama video, otherwise it takes panorama photos. The *numberOfShots* attribute allows specifying the number of shots to be taken for a panorama, in the case of photo mode. The *firstShotDelay* attribute allows to specify the interval between the command given to the payload and the first photo taken, it is specified in seconds. The photos taken are separated by time or by distance. The *timeIntervalBetweenShots* attribute specifies the time in seconds between each photo taken. The *distanceBetweenShots* attribute specifies the distance covered before the next photo is taken. The *directionAngle* attribute is used for missions such as an area scan. This attribute defines the direction of the scanning process, for example, north-south. The *angleOfRotation* attribute specifies the angle with which the camera rotates while making a panorama video or taking panorama photos. The angle is specified in degrees.

The *Goal* stereotype is applied to the resulting state of a UAV after a behavior adaptation. This behavior adaptation is also defined as an adaptation in UAS mission goals. It is an extension of the UML metaclass *State*. It is applied to a state that represents a behavior adaptation that may or may not be linked to a UAS mission goal. In case the adaptation is linked to a goal, it can either be in generic goals or mission-specific goals of the UAS. The generic goals are the ones that are common to any type of UAS mission. For example, to execute the mission, to ensure safety, or to preserve resources. The mission-specific goals are the ones that are specific to a particular mission. For example, to track fire, to spot a shark, or to monitor a car crash. This stereotype allows to model adaptation to goals in UAS mission. This adaptation is modeled as states in a UML state machine. For example, a UAV is in a traffic Monitoring state, when an over-speeding vehicle is identified. The UAV adapts its goal from *Monitoring* to *Tracking* a vehicle. As a result, the UAV moves to the *Tracking* state.

REFERENCES

- [1] Azad M Madni, Michael W Sievers, James Humann, Edwin Ordoukhanian, Barry Boehm, and Scott Lucero. Formal methods in resilient systems design: application to multi-uav system-of-systems control. In *Disciplinary convergence in systems engineering research*, pages 407–418. Springer, 2018.
- [2] Universal ground control software - ugcs. <https://www.ugcs.com/>.
- [3] Mission planner. <https://ardupilot.org/planner/>.
- [4] Qgroundcontrol - mission planning tool. <http://qgroundcontrol.com/>.